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Transformation of Food Crops into Cash Crops: A Case of Solapur District

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Abstract:

This paper studies the dynamics between cash cropping and food crop production at the district level. The paper focuses on the potential pathways by which cash crop production may affect food crop productivity and then empirically measures these effects using the case of Solapur district a major Jowar producing area. The present study is an attempt to identify the effects of cash crop production on food crop productivity in Solapur district. Solapur district is the heart of the drought prone area in Maharashtra but it is the most valuable land resources which is famous for black soil. In this district the jowar is famous for agricultural production. Solapur district is situated in south east part of Maharashtra. The area of study region is 14,895 sq.km. The study region consists of 1167 villages and has 4620205 populations in 2019. Population density is 310 people per square km. Solapur district climate in summer the maximum temperature is 42°C and minimum is 28°C and in winter the maximum temperature 27°C and minimum is 13°C.

In both year (1990-91 and 2017-18) the Jowar is major crop in the study region, but in 2017-18 the area under Jowar is decreased, because of agricultural commercialization, so cash crops became important crops in study region. The major food crops transformed into the cash crops in study region during investigation period.

Keywords: Food crops, Cash Crops, Commercialization, Agricultural Productivity, Subsistence crops

Introduction:

Food crops are any plants intentionally grown with the primary purpose of being eaten by man and animals. This definition separates a food crop from wild edible vegetation, grazing material and edible food used for any other purposes. The vast majority of store-bought fruits, vegetables and grain-based foods started in this category are included. This makes up one of the three main divisions of useful growing plants, the other two being wild plants and non-food crops. In this study region Jawar, Bajra, wheat, rice, maize and barley was the main food crops in this region. Other hand a cash crop is an agricultural crop which is grown for sale to return a profit. It is typically purchased by parties separate from a farm. The term cash crop is applied exclusively to the agricultural production of plants and animal agriculture is not a part of the terminology. The term is used to differentiate marketed crops from subsistence crops, which are those fed to the producer's own livestock or grown as food for the producer's family. In earlier times cash crops were usually only a small part of a farm's total yield, while today, especially in the developed and as well as some undeveloped countries, almost all crops are mainly grown for revenue. In least developed countries, cash crops are usually crops which attract demand in more developed nations, and hence have some export value. Sugarcane, fiber types crops, cotton and oilseeds are the main cash crops in the Solapur District.

Objectives:

The present study has been undertaken with the following specific objectives.

1. To identify the major determinants responsible for transformation of cropping pattern in district level.
2. To determine the effect of increasing crop commercialization in Solapur district.

Study Region:

Solapur district has been selected as per study which is located in western Maharashtra. The district of Solapur lies entirely in Bhima-Sina main river basin of Maharashtra state.

Map No.1
 Location Map of Solapur District

The Solapur district bounded by 17°07'N to 18°33'N latitudes and 74°37'E to 76°26'E longitudes. The total geographical area of Solapur district is 14845 sq.kms. divided into eleven tahsils. In 2019 total population of Solapur district accounts 4620205. This gives it a ranking of 43rd in India (out of total of 640). The total population accounts for 3.84 percent of the state. Solapur district has dry climate. The daily mean maximum temperature range between 30° C to 35° C and minimum temperature range between 18°C to 21°C. The highest temperature is recorded in the month of May. The average annual rainfall is registered 510 mm. The soil of the district essentially derived from the Deccan trap.

Database and Methodology:

The present investigation is based on secondary data to the study of changing pattern of cash crops and food crops in the Solapur district. The secondary data obtained from Socio-Economic Review of Solapur district from 1990-91 to 2017-18 and district Gazetteers.

Spatial Distribution of cropping pattern:

1. 1990-91:

In this year Jowar is main food crop which is 66.06%, followed by Pulses which is 11.84%. In this study area the high majority of crops are food crops. Because this time.

Graph No.1

the agricultural technology was not developed. In this year Wheat 7.70%, Bajra 4.89%, Sugarcane 3.37%, Groundnut 2.11%, Sunflower 1.31%, Cotton 0.35, fruit crops 0.41, other oil seed 1.03% and 0.93% crops are other crops. That means in this region the Jowar is main food crop, which is overall distributed. That means in this year more than 75% crops are food crops

Map No-2

The above graph indicates that the large area of food crops in 1990-91 was Madha tahsil and lowest areas were North Solapur. If we observed the above graph Karmala tahsil recorded the highest percent of cash crop and North Solapur recorded lowest percent of food crops in 1990-91.

2. 2017-18:

In this year Jowar is also main crop but the percentage is decreased (29.22%) due to the change the trend towards cash crops, Fruit crops etc. In 2017-18 the facilities of drip irrigation, new agricultural technology is the main reasons to improve the agriculture system and focused on cash crops production. So the Jowar became only 36.84% in this study region. The other crops as like wheat 1.58%, Bajra 1.80%, Maize 1.70%, Sugarcane 5.85%, Oil Seeds 6.18%, fruits 2.37% are the major crops in Solapur district.

Graph No.2

The above graph shows that Karmala tahsil was maximum area under food crops and Pandharpur tahsil recorded lowest area under food crops in 2017-18. If we think about cash crops the Akkalkot tahsil recorded the high percent and Sangola tahsil recorded lowest percent of cash crops in 2017-18.

Results and Discussion:

The finding indicates that there are major differences in performance (i.e., intensity of input use, crop productivity, and smallholder incomes) across different types of cash cropping arrangements involving private firms and smallholders in Solapur district. The more successful cash cropping arrangements between smallholders and private firms have a markedly positive effect on food crop productivity and smallholder

incomes. This emerging empirical work is beginning to indicate strongly that commercialization of smallholder agriculture, featuring high-valued cashcrops, can under certain conditions provide a strong stimulus to smallholder agriculture and havemajor indirect benefits for food crop productivity.

The principle findings of this investigation include:

1. Majority of crops in this study region were Jowar because of overall distribution of regur soil(Black Soil) in both years.
2. The proportion of Jowar crops is decreased in the 2017-18 as compare 1991-92.
3. Madha and South Solapur is the tahsils where the difference between cash crops and food crops is high, means the both tahsil are focused on food crops.
4. The areas under sugarcane increased in the year of 2017-18 due to commercialization, new agricultural technology, increase the drip irrigation etc.
5. Oilseeds also major crops in study region in 2017-18, it is 7.03%.
6. The area under fruits also increasedfrom 0.41 to 2.37%.
7. In this study region Jowar, Bajra, Wheat, Maize is major crops in both years.
8. Commercialization was significantly positively affected by farm size, other factors held constant, but farm size was significantly inversely related to food crop productivity.
9. Overall, the findings show that farm dynamics between cash cropping, capital investment, andfood crop output, are important to consider in discussions of agricultural commercializationamong smallholder farmers. Two key pathways have been identified by which cropcommercialization may improve food crop productivity.

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